

HARNESS CITIZEN KNOWLEDGE FOR POLICY IMPACT

How citizen science data and action can drive successful environmental compliance assurance.

In a Nutshell

This series of policy briefs examines areas in which citizen generated data and actions can make a direct and key contribution to meeting policy targets:

- On **plastic pollution**, community monitoring can inform the evaluation of the Single-Use Plastics Directive and support more effective enforcement.
- On **deforestation**, local communities' data can strengthen country risk benchmarking under the EUDR and reveal risks overlooked in official datasets.
- On **water quality**, citizen science can help Member States meet the 2027 good ecological status target under the Water Framework Directive by providing timely, local monitoring.
- On **pollinators**, citizen-led actions can help authorities move from recognising pollinator decline to delivering targeted, evidence-based impact.

Environmental compliance assurance is at a crossroads. Ambitious global objectives, EU legislation and national policies addressing biodiversity loss, pollution and deforestation continue to advance, yet a gap remains between regulatory ambition and practical implementation. Often, authorities lack timely data, local insight, or sufficient monitoring capacity to detect pressures, respond quickly, and verify compliance by duty holders.

Meanwhile, communities across the world are generating robust evidence, documenting environmental change and acting to protect

the ecosystems on which they rely. These contributions are not peripheral; they are essential.

Citizen science and community-led actions can strengthen environmental compliance in ways that public authorities cannot achieve alone. They extend the reach of observation and monitoring, add local knowledge that would otherwise be missed, and enable early detection of risks. They can also enhance accountability, expose implementation gaps, and strengthen public trust in environmental decision-making.

more4nature aims to bring about transformative change in environmental protection by including citizens and communities as key actors in collaborative environmental compliance assurance with public authorities. Integrating citizen science into formal processes raises important questions about data quality, comparability, governance, and responsibility. These issues must be addressed, and more4nature is committed to doing so. However, high-quality community knowledge should be used without delay where it already exists and is directly relevant to compliance assurance.

We therefore invite national, European and global environmental policy makers and regulators to consider these proposals as practical opportunities to reinforce the very objectives they are entrusted to deliver.

Get in touch!

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